

Influence of modified urea and placement on N use in irrigated rice

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Numerous N response experiments have shown that fertilizer N recovery by rice is seldom higher than 30-40%; even with the best agronomic practices and strictly controlled conditions, recovery seldom exceeds 60-65%. Using urea supergranules (USG) or urea briquettes, deep placed, has increased N efficiency, and crop response to sulfur-coated urea (SCU) has generally been superior to response to urea in a single dose and often to split applications.

We compared the efficiency of SCU, USG, and best split urea at different N levels in a randomized block design with four replications. The 4-yr experiment (1981-84) used medium-duration Asha and Usha as test varieties. Soil was a Vertisol, clay loam texture, with pH 7.0, 1.3% organic matter, 11% total N, and CEC 33 meq/100 g. Exchange-

Grain yield with different modified urea materials, placement techniques, and nitrogen levels. Raipur, India (1981-84 wet seasons).

N(kg/ha)	Urea form ^a	Grain yield(t/ha)				
		1981	1982	1983	1984	Mean
0	-	2.0	2.6	1.9	2.0	2.1
29	PU	2.3	3.1	2.7	-	2.7
58	PU	2.4	3.6	3.0	3.9	3.2
87	PU	2.8	3.4	3.4	4.4	3.5
116	PU	2.9	3.9	3.7	4.4	3.7
Mean	PU	2.6	3.5	3.2	4.2	3.4
29	SCU	2.6	3.3	3.2	-	3.0
58	SCU	3.1	4.0	3.8	4.0	3.7
87	SCU	3.2	4.0	4.2	4.2	3.9
116	SCU	3.7	4.4	4.5	4.5	4.3
Mean	SCU	3.2	3.9	3.9	4.3	3.8
29	USG	2.4	3.6	3.2	-	3.1
58	USG	2.7	3.6	3.7	4.3	3.6
87	USG	2.8	4.1	4.1	4.6	3.9
116	USG	3.1	3.6	4.3	4.8	4.0
Mean	USG	2.7	3.7	3.8	4.6	3.7
LSD (0.05)		0.4	0.7	0.4	2.6	
CV (%)		9.5	11.2	7.2	10.5	

^aPU was applied as best split, SCU was broadcast and incorporated, USG was placed 10-12cm deep in the soil

able bases (in meq/100 g) were 0.07 Na, 0.63 K, 4.7 Mg, and 27 Ca. Available P was 17 ppm by Bray method and 4 ppm by Olsen. Available Zn was 2.7 ppm.

Maximum yields at all N levels were obtained with SCU broadcast and incorporated, followed by USG placed

10-12 cm deep, and prilled urea (PU) best split (see table). Yields increased with increased N.

Highest N use efficiency was 32.1 kg grain/kg N as USG at 29 kg N/ha. Averaged over N levels, maximum N use efficiency was 18.7 kg grain/kg N as SCU. ■

Influence of modified urea materials at different N rates on estimated wetland rice soil ammonium-N and nitrate-N

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Changes in $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ levels in wetland soil can provide valuable insights into N losses and availability of N for rice. The $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ at 0-15 cm depth in flooded soil were measured at 15, 30, 45, and 60 d after transplanting (DT).

The experimental area was Aquic Hapludoll (Mollisol of Tarai moist plains region about 30 km south of the foothills of the Shivalik Range of the Himalayas). Soil was silt loam with pH 7.9, 1.2% organic C, 0.1% total N, 8 ppm available

1. $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ content in soil as influenced by N rates (a) and sources (b).

NH₄⁺-N, and 10 ppm available NO₃⁻-N. Pant Dhan 4 (134 d duration) was transplanted during 1985 and 1986 wet seasons (May-Oct).

Urea supergranule (USG), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and Musoorie phospho-coated urea (MPCU) as basal incorporated and prilled urea (PU) applied as local split (1/2 at transplanting, 1/4 at tillering, 1/4 at 5-6 d before panicle initiation [DBPI]) and standard split (2/3 at transplanting and 1/3 at 5-6 DBPI) were applied at 29, 58, and 87 kg N/ha. MPCU and SCU were broadcast and incorporated at transplanting, USG was hand placed 8-10 cm deep in the center of 4 hills.

Soil samples were collected randomly from fertilized plots, except in USG plots where they were collected 6-8 cm away from the placement site.

NH₄⁺-N and NO₃⁻-N were extracted from the wet soil immediately with 1N sodium sulfate. NH₄⁺-N concentration was determined by modified Nessler reagent method and that of NO₃⁻-N by chromotropic acid method.

NH₄⁺-N content increased with increasing N rates to 30 DT, then decreased (Fig. 1). The decrease may be attributed to uptake by plants, gaseous loss of NH₃, and nitrification-denitrification. The decrease was less with USG.

NO₃⁻-N concentration was very low. At 15 DT, it was higher with PU and MPCU than with USG and SCU (Fig. 2). Plots with USG showed lower NO₃⁻-N, presumably because the USG was placed in a reduced zone where nitrification might be limited for lack of oxygen. With SCU, low concentration of NO₃⁻-N could be due to delayed release of urea and conversion of fertilizer N to NO₃⁻.

2. NO₃⁻-N content in soil as influenced by N rates (a) and sources (b).

The presence of nitrate suggests that nitrification-denitrification losses may be occurring.

These results suggest that formation of soil nitrate can be reduced slightly through the use of modified urea materials. ■

Contribution of flood siltation to boro rice yield and response to N and K

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Floodwater deposits silt and other suspended materials as it starts to recede. The effects of this silting on soil productivity have not been established experimentally.

We evaluated the effects of siltation by floodwater on boro rice in terms of the crop's response to N and K fertilizer Jan-Apr 1988. Land within the Hathazari Farming Systems Research area was

ponded by floodwater about 1.5 m deep for about 15 d.

After the flood receded, three types of soil sampling were done: deposited surface silts, 2.5 cm; original soil, 2.5-15

Table 1. Characteristics of soil sample of flash-flooded ricefields Hathazari, Bangladesh Jan 1988.

Soil sample	pH	Organic matter (%)	K (meq/100 ml)	NH ₄ -N (lg/ml)	Zn (lg/ml)	S (lg/ml)
0-2.5 cm surface silt	6.6	2.35	1.0	22.5	3.0	8
2.5-15 cm soil	5.9	2.45	0.3	17.5	2.5	4
0-15 cm silt and soil	6.0	2.50	0.3	19.5	3.0	7